

Information in the Universe

Positive and Negative Aspects of my Theory
(Version 3)

My theory posits that the universe is comprised of information that is perfectly conserved and has both positive and negative aspects. Here's an overview of the positive and negative facets as outlined:

Positive Aspects

1. Perfect Recreation

Potential for Precise Resurrection: My theory suggests that since information is infinite and perfect in DNA, it allows for the potential to recreate a person precisely. This means resurrecting the exact individual that once existed, not just creating a clone.

2. Information in Every Particle

Universal Recreation: I propose that information is infinite not only in DNA but in every atom, particle, and even within the vacuum of space. This implies the possibility of recreating/resurrecting a person not only from their DNA, but also using random particles in the universe due to the theoretical similarity of information across particles.

Negative Aspects

1. Unprovable Existence of Infinity

Theoretical Limitations: A significant downside is that proving the existence of infinity in the real world is impossible, even over billions or trillions of years. Infinity is a mathematical concept that cannot be empirically demonstrated in the physical world.

2. Inaccessibility of Complete Information

Practical Limitations: Even if infinity were proven to exist, accessing all of it would be impossible because an infinite sequence has no end. This suggests that no matter how much information is extracted from DNA or particles, access will always be limited to a finite amount, never encompassing the entirety of infinite information.

Conclusion

My theory presents ideas about the nature of information in the universe and its implications for recreating/resurrecting individuals or phenomena. The concept of infinity and its relationship with information challenges our understanding and poses fundamental questions about the limits of human empirical inquiry and comprehension. The theory suggests a universe where

information is not only foundational but also limitless and perpetually conserved, opening up speculative possibilities for resurrection and recreation but also highlighting the inherent limitations and challenges in proving and accessing infinite information.

Note

This manuscript was written with the help of ChatGPT.

Copyright

Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
05/29/2024